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**JOB SATISFACTION AMONG MEDICAL
DOCTORS**

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ABSTRACT:

Job satisfaction or employee satisfaction is a measure of workers' contentedness with their job, whether they like the job or individual aspects or facets of jobs, such as nature of work or supervision. Job satisfaction can be measured in cognitive (evaluative), affective (or emotional), and behavioral components. Researchers have also noted that job satisfaction measures vary in the extent to which they measure feelings about the job (affective job satisfaction). or cognitions about the job (cognitive job satisfaction).

One of the most widely used definitions in organizational research is that of Locke (1976), who defines job satisfaction as "a pleasurable or positive emotional state resulting from the appraisal of one's job or job experiences" Others have defined it as simply how content an individual is with his or her job; whether he or she likes the job.

Keywords: Job Satisfaction

INTRODUCTION:

Job satisfaction or employee satisfaction is a measure of workers' contentedness with their job, whether they like the job or individual aspects or facets of jobs, such as nature of work or supervision. Job satisfaction can be measured in cognitive (evaluative), affective (or emotional), and behavioral components. Researchers have also noted that job satisfaction measures vary in the extent to which they measure feelings about the job (affective job satisfaction). or cognitions about the job (cognitive job satisfaction).

One of the most widely used definitions in organizational research is that of Locke (1976), who defines job satisfaction as "a pleasurable or positive emotional state resulting from the appraisal of one's job or job experiences" Others have defined it as simply how content an individual is with his or her job; whether he or she likes the job.

It is assessed at both the global level (whether the individual is satisfied with the job overall), or at the facet level (whether the individual is satisfied with different aspects of the job). Spector (1997) lists 14 common facets: appreciation, communication, coworkers, fringe benefits, Job conditions, nature of the work, organization, personal growth, policies and procedures, promotion opportunities, recognition, security, and supervision.

Hulin and Judge (2003) have noted that job satisfaction includes multidimensional psychological responses to an individual's job, and that these personal responses have cognitive (evaluative), affective (or emotional), and behavioral components. Job satisfaction scales vary in the extent to which they assess the affective feelings about the job or the cognitive assessment of the job. Affective job satisfaction is a subjective construct representing an emotional feeling individuals have about their job. Hence, affective job

satisfaction for individuals reflects the degree of pleasure or happiness their job in general induces.

Cognitive job satisfaction is a more objective and logical evaluation of various facets of a job. Cognitive job satisfaction can be unidimensional if it comprises evaluation of just one facet of a job, such as pay or maternity leave, or multidimensional if two or more facets of a job are simultaneously evaluated. Cognitive job satisfaction does not assess the degree of pleasure or happiness that arises from specific job facets, but rather gauges the extent to which those job facets are judged by the job holder to be satisfactory in comparison with objectives they themselves set or with other jobs. While cognitive job satisfaction might help to bring about affective job satisfaction, the two constructs are distinct, not necessarily directly related, and have different antecedents and consequences.

Job satisfaction can also be seen within the broader context of the

range of issues which affect an individual's experience of work, or their quality of working life. Job satisfaction can be understood in terms of its relationships with other key factors, such as general well-being, stress at work, control at work, home-work interface, and working conditions.

The assessment of job satisfaction through employee anonymous surveys became commonplace in the 1930s. Although prior to that time there was the beginning of interest in employee attitudes, there were only a handful of studies published. Latham and Budworth note that Uhrbrock in 1934 was one of the first psychologists to use the newly developed attitude measurement techniques to assess factory worker attitudes. They also note that in 1935 Hoppock conducted a study that focused explicitly on job satisfaction that is affected by both the nature of the job and relationships with coworkers and supervisors.

DISCUSSION:

According to a study by Mrduljaš et al., there were no significant differences between family physicians and hospital specialists in total job satisfaction ($F = 1.02$; $p = 0.41$). Family physicians were more satisfied with their workplace conditions than internal medicine specialists (19.37 ± 4.23 vs. 17.37 ± 4.59 ; $F = 5.93$; $p = 0.003$), and less satisfied with the possibilities for postgraduate training than surgeons (5.27 ± 1.90 vs. 6.59 ± 2.07 ; $F = 9.26$; $p < 0.001$). Global job satisfaction was rather low but does not differ between the three medical groups. Disparities were observed in some segments (opportunity for further training and academic advancement, vacation, and salary). The reason for the family physician's relative satisfaction may be due to stable working conditions, independence in organizing work schedules and personal responsibility (4).

According to Atif et al., amongst the respondents, 10 (10.3%) doctors had below average job satisfaction, 32(33.0%), 21(21.6%), 21(21.6%) and 13(13.3%) had average, above average, well above average and outstanding job satisfaction respectively. There was significant relation between job satisfaction and age group of the doctors ($p 0.025$), education ($p 0.015$), service years ($p 0.013$) income per month ($p < 0.001$). There was no significant impact of gender ($p 0.540$), marital status ($p 0.087$), number of children ($p 0.153$), current employment ($p 0.71$), nature of job ($p 0.204$), working hours ($p 0.089$), additional duties ($p 0.421$) and socioeconomic class ($p 0.104$) on outcome variable (5).

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